

Persephone's poetry

When you read 16 poems in a row, there is a fair chance to overlook the best one. This is what happened with Persephone by Janine Soucie Kelley. With this review I will try to make up for my initial mistake.

The title steers us into the direction of Greek mythology; to the grieving goddess Demeter whose daughter – Persephone- has been lost to Hades and the underworld. Eventually, a compromise is made and the year equally split, in which the girl accompanies Hades during one part and is reunited with her mother in the other months. Happiness dominates the period the family spends together, and Demeter blesses the world with warmth and light. Summer. The time in separation though, causes her heart to turn cold, and so does the earth.

“Winter”. This statement opens the poem and we immediately know where we are; in the mother's desperate season. But then the author follows with “Christmas”, so we are tossed from Classic mythology to western religion. Throughout the poem, J. Kelley constantly alternates between the Old and New tales to have them eventually merged. This surely has happened before; on expansion of the Roman empire the celebration of the Holy child was conveniently combined with local traditions welcoming the new light after the shortest day had passed. An indication of how cultural stories tell about universal feelings or phenomena, rendering them interchangeable in that regard.

A mother writes the words, while mourning over her daughter (she's only thirteen; can we handle one more (superstitious) belief?) who's horribly sick and “lost in hell”. This is a wink to the Greek legend, but the deal between Hades and Demeter reflects itself also in the girl being “half-asleep”, a “half-mad mother” and the poem cut up in halves. Even the pharmaceuticals are Classical, with “Latin and Greek names”. Prompt the author offers an exciting personification of these “names riding through” her veins. Perhaps on chariots, because it is war! Cancer is war, and “terrible drugs” are used in combat. Illness drags a person down to a bed, the floor or even lower, into the ground. There it is cold like winter and “the sun is dark”. Conceptual metaphors like these are tools to recognize a certain sentiment, just like we can all convey the unpredictable nature of wild beasts to the image of “cancer like a wolf”. The wolf is “howling”, thus announcing bad tidings. This might be the only occasion where the writer momentarily steps away from her carefully set-up theme and coherence in myth and religion.

But back to the story; we relate bad experiences and death with everything that is “under” and dark. Naturally, we connect joy and hope with the orientation “up” and brightness. So, in the second part of the poem optimism seems to return when mother and daughter “watch the sky”. The Christmas tale returns too, where “stars, small covenants of light” assure the way to new life and hope. “Snow” and its whiteness transfer the idea of cleansing and serenity. The girl is cleansed like a Buddhist monk with “a shaven head” (yes, we can handle one more religion). Dressed in white, the “nurses, pale angels” carry out the Script of the newest (and I promise: the last) religion, Science. Hope and trust are projected onto medical therapies as readily as people place their faith in any God.

Here in the hospital bed, the young girl may have skipped many seasons of her life, approaching its end. Like the Christmas tale in fast-forward to Easter, and “like Christ” she will succumb to fate and “say nothing”. It makes sense; the resurrection meant a new beginning, just like winter announces a new summer. “Carols” and “promises of Bethlehem and kings” will hopefully terminate the goddess of agriculture's “mad myth” and the light of spring will touch the seeds of renewed life. Soon health can be harvested.

The intertwinement of Greek myth and Christianity is established in so much detail that the reader can find a reference in almost every line. These cultural metaphors are highly effective in transmitting the feelings of grief. Besides a painfully beautiful illustration of chemotherapy (“nurses, pale angels, anchor your arms to more machines”), the author has found a fluid rhythm in her short, efficient lines. She mostly accomplished melody through internal, partial rhymes. The entire last phrase for example, breathes a unity of sound (“skin, whisper, promises, kings, this myth, spring”). This poem is a truly intricately work of craft, art and love.

(The Cancer Project, page 174)

PERSEPHONE

For Vanessa

By Janine Soucie Kelley

It is winter. Christmas.
And you are half asleep
from the terrible drugs
with mysterious Latin
and Greek names riding
through your veins – one
means place of death.
Like half-mad Demeter,
I grieve for a daughter lost
in hell. Thirteen.
This was to be the season
of your first dance, a first
kiss – but cancer like a wolf
has come howling to your bed.
The sun is dark, all
innocence lost, and life
more cruel than any legend.

I wait and pray, the stars
small covenants of light.
From the hospital window,
we watch the sky.
It is snowing. The first snow.
Nurses, pale angels, come and go
to take your pulse,
to count your blood,
to anchor your arms to more machines.
Like Christ, you say nothing.
I touch your face, your shaven head,
and trace the soul beneath your skin.
You smile. I whisper carols